

Teachers' Learning Assessment Capability And Students' Classroom Satisfaction In Cluster 2 Schools, Davao City

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Abstract. The study of teachers' learning assessment capability sought to measure students' classroom satisfaction. The study's respondents were the secondary school teachers in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division, and the 176 junior high school students were selected as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized to select the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' learning assessment capability and students' classroom satisfaction were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a positive significant relationship between teachers' learning assessment capability and students' classroom satisfaction. Regression analysis proved that teachers' learning assessment capability in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment was a significant predictor of students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. In other words, teachers' learning assessment capability influences students' satisfaction with the virtual learning environment. However, the researcher recommends further analyzing the factors affecting the students' classroom satisfaction since teachers' learning assessment capability only contributed 43.00 percent to the total variability.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher's learning assessment capability
2. students' classroom satisfaction
3. virtual learning environment

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1. Introduction

Modern technologies are contributing to the dissolution of traditional classroom boundaries. Students connect with their instructors and each other through modalities of almost every variety, greatly expanding avenues of communication. Students' classroom satisfaction has been shown to be a reliable proxy for measuring the success of implementing ICT-based initiatives in e-learning environments. Scholars have documented a strong relationship between how students perceive their academic performance and how satisfied students are with their varied learning environments. This pandemic has challenged educational institutions around the world since varied modalities require physical equipment such as computers, servers, learning and communication platforms, but also software applications, operating systems, and experts in the use of these technologies. However, teachers must also possess sufficient digital compe-

tencies if they are to use different modalities effectively in the learning process. As defined by Metin (2011), a teacher's learning assessment capability is the measurement of skills, performance, and beliefs that reflect real-world situations and require the students to develop their original responses explaining the processes followed in order to achieve those results. Likewise, Alsafi (2011) argues that when teachers incorporate performance assessment that fits the learning styles of the students into their classroom by identifying the learning styles of each of their students and matching the teaching style to the learning style for difficult tasks, it increases students' capabilities and strength followed by enhancing the effectiveness of learning experience. Also, Taha et al. (2020) viewed that the classroom learning environment for adolescent students, as reported in the literature, allows easy accessibility to knowledge, proper content delivery, content standardization, personalized instruction, self-pacing, interactivity, and increased convenience. Classroom learning set-up has been used as an adjunct method to augment the classical approach to teaching. The sudden transition from one teaching modality to another is courtesy of COVID-19. Moreover, several studies indicated a significant relationship between teachers' learning assessment capability and students' classroom satisfaction. For instance, Ugras et al. (2012) the result revealed that there is a relationship between teachers' learning assessment capability and students' satisfaction in the learning environment. The result shows that satisfaction in the classroom could be established by connecting teacher's skills and knowledge about various assessment tools and techniques. Also, Pham et al. (2019) proposed that a teacher's ability to integrate technology into the curriculum affects learning student satisfaction, which in turn, positively affects learning student loyalty. However, student's dissatisfaction with the classroom environment remains a challenge that

needs to be addressed among educators worldwide. For instance, Tidman (2021) reported that between 33 percent and 50 percent of students were unhappy with the learning environment setup because of the bulk of work, less time overall in class, teacher-centered approach, and assessment issues, and made examinations and assessments, particularly difficult and potentially unfair. Similarly, McIntyre (2020) reported that a survey showed that one-third of 4,178 students were not satisfied with the learning environment, and forty-five percent felt the quality of their education was not good. Taking things in the Philippines setting, Barrot et al. (2021) reported that majority of the Filipino students were not satisfied with different learning sets up due to some of the learning challenges faced by students, such as adaptability, technical issues, computer knowledge, distraction, and self-motivation. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in a first congressional district in Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made use of descriptive-correlational design to have a better understanding of the student's learning interest as determined by technology usage, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding classroom satisfaction in the context of students in the Division of Davao City. Besides, the results of the study may serve as available data for planners in educational institutions in making enhancement programs regarding those aspects of teachers' learning assessment capability domains that may enhance students' classroom satisfaction.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

This section reviews relevant literature on teachers' learning assessment capability and students' classroom satisfaction, drawing from various studies to highlight key indicators such as performance assessment, attitudes, and communi-

cation.

1.1.1. Teachers' Learning Assessment Capability—Metin (2011) defines this capability as teachers' skills and attitudes in assessing students' real-world performance. Yu (2014) and Shehadeh (2012) emphasize the role of performance assessment in fostering authentic learning, while Jalbani (2014) and Alsafi (2011) argue that effective assessment strategies enhance student engagement and cater to diverse learning styles.

Zelley et al. (2015) and Dörnyei Ushioda (2011) link teachers' positive attitudes toward performance assessments with increased learner autonomy and motivation. Nier et al. (2014) highlight mismatches in expectations between teachers and students, stressing the importance of aligning assessment with real-life skills.

Korpershoek et al. (2014) and Nasey (2012) discuss classroom discipline, motivation, and behavior management as contributors to performance. Oscarson (2014) and McTighe (2011) view assessment as integral to the learning process, while Jorge (2013), Abella (2011), and Rhamna (2012) support performance-based methods like presentations and projects for holistic evaluation.

Attitudes toward authentic assessment shape the way teachers prepare tools that measure higher-order thinking (Abby, 2010; Yara, 2011; Pean, 2014). According to Jorge (2013) and Lao (2015), performance assessment promotes skills such as inquiry and collaboration, though no single approach fits all (Maio Haddock, 2010).

Self and peer assessment also play a role. Alufohai Akinlosotu (2016) and Olatomide Oluwatosin (2014) show that these methods promote reflective and independent learning. Teachers must guide students through these processes (Muñoz Alvarez, 2007; Oscarsson, 2009; Tshabalala Ndimande, 2016).

1.1.2. Students' Classroom Satisfaction—Hamutoglu et al. (2018) define classroom satisfaction as students' positive response to inter-

active, technology-supported learning. Elshami et al. (2021) and Martin (2018) show that satisfaction is tied to motivation, communication, feedback, and instructor quality.

Studies by Alawamleh Al-twait (2020), Dziuban et al. (2016), and Gómez-Rey et al. (2016) suggest that a satisfying environment boosts engagement and academic performance. Conversely, dissatisfaction hinders learning (Coman et al., 2020). Kurucay Inan (2017) and Cheon et al. (2020) note that both student and faculty satisfaction affect learning quality.

Online learning offers flexibility and convenience (Cole et al., 2019; Landrum et al., 2020), though issues like time zones can affect satisfaction (Fish Snodgrass, 2016). Interaction remains vital (Cidral et al., 2018; Gopal et al., 2020; Alamri Tyler-Wood, 2017).

Satisfaction hinges on factors such as course design and interactivity (Asoodar et al., 2016; Himmelsbach, 2021). Interaction quality strongly predicts satisfaction (Quiang, 2018; Ke Kwak, 2013), and digital tools can enhance engagement (Hillmayr et al., 2020).

Communication is key for distance learning success (Kayode, 2018; Hettiarachchi Wickramasinghe, 2016). Osaat Nsereka (2013) and Dintoe (2018) emphasize that effective communication builds social ties crucial for collaboration.

Contribution refers to how virtual learning satisfaction improves education quality (Hettiarachchi Wickramasinghe, 2016). Tools and flexibility boost engagement (Sun et al., 2016; Alawamleh et al., 2020). Ugras et al. (2012) found a strong link between teacher assessment competence and student satisfaction, while Battersby Cave (2014) connect self-efficacy to positive assessment practices.

1.2. Synthesis—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the discussions of literature and the result of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the

literature showed that a teacher's learning assessment capability is measured in terms of attitude towards using quality of performance assessment, attitude towards authentic assessment, and self and peer assessment, while students' classroom satisfaction is measured in terms of satisfaction, communication, and contribution. Also, studies derived from several theoretical perspectives have confirmed a number of assumptions about teachers' learning assessment capability is connected with students' classroom satisfaction. This gives the author sufficient background to understand the study. Assessment is part of practical planning for both teaching and learning, which means that teachers require the professional knowledge and skills to plan for assessment, observe learning, analyze and interpret evidence of learning, give feedback to learners, and support learners as they assess themselves. Likewise, Assessment pushes instruction by stressing the importance of critical thinking, reasoning, and reflection, thus creating a quality learning environment. Many techniques may be used to assess student learning outcomes. On the other hand, when the students feel satisfied with their experience and education, they're more likely to remain engaged in the curriculum, finish their programs, and reach graduation. High levels of student satisfaction can help you reach campus initiatives and drive change at your institution. The empirical literature on student satisfaction and academic performance proves these two constructs are positively correlated. Undergraduate economics students who are more satisfied with their educational experiences tend to achieve higher levels of academic performance. Moreover, Student satisfaction is a quality indicator that education institutions must closely monitor. An important quality indicator for education institutions is student satisfaction. It assesses how much students enjoy classes and their experience with an institution. Furthermore, the relationship between teachers' learning assessment

capability and students' classroom satisfaction is vital for enhancing the overall learning experience for students in several ways. Such as Effective Feedback which means teachers adept at assessing student learning can provide specific and actionable feedback to help students understand their strengths and areas for improvement. This personalized feedback can significantly enhance the learning process and boost student satisfaction. Like Tailored Instruction which means the proficient assessment skills enable teachers to tailor their instruction to meet students' individual needs. Teachers can create a more engaging and inclusive learning environment by employing different teaching strategies based on assessment data, leading to higher student satisfaction. Similarly, their connection can also support Student Empowerment, like involving students in the assessment process through self-assessments or peer assessments, promotes student ownership over their learning journey. This empowerment can increase student satisfaction as they feel more engaged and invested in their academic growth, and a positive classroom environment, which effective assessment practices contribute to a positive classroom climate where students feel supported and valued in their learning endeavors. When students perceive that their progress is recognized and encouraged, they are likelier to feel comfortable, engaged, and satisfied within the learning environment, and most importantly, a Continuous Improvement in which teachers who proficiently assess student learning can identify areas for improvement, both for students and their teaching practices. By utilizing assessment data to refine instructional strategies, teachers can create a dynamic learning environment that continuously evolves to meet students' needs and enhance their satisfaction. When assessments are conducted in a supportive and constructive manner, students are more likely to feel confident in their abilities and less stressed about academic performance, contributing to an over-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study Statement of the Problem

all positive learning experience. Educators can create a more enriching and fulfilling learning environment that supports student growth and success by recognizing the significance of teachers' assessment capabilities in shaping students' classroom satisfaction.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on the proposition of Ugras et al. (2012) that satisfaction could be established by connecting teachers' skills and knowledge about various assessment tools and techniques. Thus, it is essential for a teacher to have a good command of the concepts in performance assessment, certain skills, and positive attitudes in order for them to evaluate and develop their own teaching methods and reach fewer value judgments. In support, Pham et al. (2019) proposed that a teacher's ability to integrate technology into the curriculum affects learning student satisfaction, which in turn, positively affects learning student loyalty. Accordingly, teachers who are equipped with knowledge in the learning environment assist students in higher education in completing various tasks and research. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable of the study is the teacher's learning assessment capability or the teacher's ability to make and executing performance assessments to students that will help them grow in the

right direction and support their progress toward learning goals. The measures of teacher's learning assessment capability according to Metin (2011) are quality of performance assessment or the attitude in preparing and applying the performance assessment that requires students to demonstrate acquisition of knowledge and skills in one or more content areas; attitude towards authentic assessment or the teachers' attitude on a performance assessment tool that was being used in the class; and self and peer assessment or teachers' attitude when applying self and peer assessment to learners where learners undergo an evaluation process on how they will judge their own achievements about their own personal criteria. The dependent variable is students' classroom satisfaction. The measures of students' classroom satisfaction, according to Hamutoglu et al. (2018), are satisfaction or the extent to which the learners are satisfied with the instructor, learner, technology, course, design, environment, communication, or the effective sharing of information which resulted in a shared understanding, and contribution or the contribution of virtual learning environment satisfaction to the quality in education, students' motivation and satisfaction, learning performance, interaction and/or communication among students, and between students and teachers.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine which domains of teachers’ learning assessment capability significantly influence the students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of teachers’ learning assessment capability in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City in terms of:
 - (1) quality of performance assessment;
 - (2) attitude towards authentic assessment; and
 - (3) self and peer assessment?
- (2) What is the extent of students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City in terms of:
 - (1) satisfaction;
 - (2) communication; and
 - (3) contribution?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between teacher’s learning assessment capability and students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City?
- (4) Which domain of the teacher’s learning assessment capability influences students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ learning assessment capability and students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City. H02: None of the domains of the teacher’s learning assessment capability influence students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City. The current study will focus on teacher’s learning assessment capability to improve the students’ classroom satisfaction in the Cluster 2 schools in Davao City. Thus, the study would benefit the following organizations and individuals: School Leaders. School leaders would benefit because establishing the significant influence of these variables may provide a framework that aimed at producing an engaging learning environment. The findings of the study may be of interest to school leaders and educational development, as satisfaction is a key differentiator in a competitive marketplace and crucial for improvement. Policy Makers. The findings of the current study could be beneficial for planning, designing, and delivering learning activities, and it could increase student and faculty satisfaction with courses and, consequently, the quality of learning. Hence, this study provides a synthesis of both approaches. Teachers. The results would benefit the teachers since they generate facts, which is important in providing a competitive classroom environment. Correspondingly, they would increase student engagement. To increase satisfaction and future improvement, the study recommends a combination of synchronous and asynchronous approaches, incorporating different applications with the learning management systems used to engage students in learning. Future researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research on classroom satisfaction and teacher learning assessment capability. Also, the findings of this study will be baseline data for future studies and may contribute to the scarcity of correlational studies in relation to these variables. For a more comprehensive understanding, the follow-

ing terms were defined operationally: Teacher's Learning Assessment Capability. This study describes the independent variable in terms of attitude towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitude towards authentic as-

essment, and attitude towards self- and peer assessment. Students' Classroom Satisfaction. This study refers to the dependent variable being described in terms of the following indicators: satisfaction, communication, and contribution.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It was formed from a deductive approach that emphasizes theory testing, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacked the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Creswell (2013), descriptive correlational research is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. In this study, the researcher would examine the teacher's learning assessment capability and the students' classroom satisfaction. Specifically, the study would investigate the study focused on the relationships among variables to determine the significance of the relationships between these variables. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher would not experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the secondary school teachers in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division. The 176 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. This study implemented specific inclusion criteria to determine the study's respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division who voluntarily signed the ICF, were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the performance rating of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents. The instrument was divided into two parts. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments. The first part of the instrument concerned with the teacher's capability, which was adopted from the study of Metin (2011),

indicated with the quality of performance assessment, attitude towards authentic assessment, and self and peer assessment. The reliability of the original scale was 0.833, which made it re-

liable. The adapted instrument is composed of 30 statements and would make use of a 5-point Likert scale that was determined based on the following ranges of means:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher’s learning assessment capability is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher’s learning assessment capability is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher’s learning assessment capability is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher’s learning assessment capability is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher’s learning assessment capability is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was about students’ classroom satisfaction. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Hamutoglu et al. (2018). This instrument indicates students’ classroom satisfaction with satisfaction, communication, and contribution. Cron-

bach’s alpha coefficient for the original scale was 0.946, which means it was very reliable and consistent. The instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale that was determined based on the following range of mean:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The student’s classroom satisfaction is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The student’s classroom satisfaction is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The student’s classroom satisfaction is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The student’s classroom satisfaction is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The student’s classroom satisfaction is never evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher took steps to conduct the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher wrote a permission letter to the Division Of-

fice of Davao City, allowing her study to be conducted. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. Upon the approval from the Division Office, the

endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division. The researchers personally brought the letters to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher first appeared at the principal's office in the third week of January 2023. However, the researcher was not able to receive some of the approval from the respective office due to the busy schedules of some principals. So, the researcher returned in the fourth week of January 2023 to follow up on the approval from the respective office. The approval from the respective offices was then granted. After this, the researcher proceeded to distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. This was done on February 7-9, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the questionnaire administration, the researcher distributed the questionnaires following health protocols. The study participants were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Each score was then subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors

were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study.

Social Value – Research was crucial to society, particularly in education. This study focuses on the collaborative support system among teachers and their motivation, specifically for elementary educators. The researcher was particularly interested in how teachers' instructional efficacy influences students' reading and comprehension of digital text. The results could inform policymakers to create programs that benefit student learning. The researcher views social value as essential for ethical research, highlighting the anticipated benefits for society or participants. Ethical considerations protect the rights and welfare of participants, addressing issues such as anonymity, the avoidance of personally identifiable information, and maintaining confidentiality.

Informed Consent – The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through a written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them for a better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that the respondent's involvement in the study is voluntary. If ever they would refuse to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to survey the factors that hinder/promote the students' classroom satisfaction about teachers' learning assessment capability in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City and may contribute to the enhancement.

Vulnerability of Research Participants – The study's respondents were teachers, so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them are

of legal age and are not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead of time that they might withdraw their participation in the study. If any inconvenience was felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given a chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were all of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher was a secondary school teacher in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division, as one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so they would not be vulnerable while participating in this study. Researcher considered the school teachers' participants in this study because they were mature enough to decide whether to participate.

Privacy and Confidentiality – This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, which was the real source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person that could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety – In administer-

ing the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and thoroughly and properly explained the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. The researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire to minimize inconvenience. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as a respondent to the study if they thought that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study.

Justice – To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher did not discriminate in selecting the study respondents—anybody with the qualifications of being a permanent regular in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting them as little as possible during their routine. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of

their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for the data used and the costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed of the study's objectives before they were involved in the process. They were emphasized as the data source and encouraged to give honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority for the benefits of the possible offshoots of the study findings.

Transparency – To provide transparency in this study, any communication related to the research was done with honesty and openness. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by ensuring that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially the information that has a bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The participants can access and scrutinize the study's findings to determine if the findings were scientifically valid and have significant implications for the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and with accuracy. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community.

Qualification of the Researcher – The researcher ensured that other factors like the con-

flict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. The respondents, parents, and school administrators of the participating schools could access the study's findings because the information would be made available if they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success; the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so it can be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study.

Adequacy of Facilities – The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and ample and available learning materials. The study was conducted within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the respondents' ratings properly during the day, when the researcher was not too tired to do so, to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. The researcher adequately has the budget and equipment to conduct the study. This was to ensure that the researcher had the best facilities to complete the research. The researcher personally owned the laptop, printer, internet connection, and other facilities, making the facilities adequately and readily available. Furthermore, non-online and online library resources are readily available, such as books and Google. In addition, Google Meet was used to gather data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts, like the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members, who are also the expert validators, provided the researcher with the guidance needed in conducting this research.

Community Involvement – It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in

making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The researcher is engaged with the secondary school teachers in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City Division. The community comprises quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects its cultural, traditional, and religious practices. The RMC graduate school helped correct, validate, and revise the current study's manuscript and provided directions to the researcher based on its research standards and practices. The study's output shows the involvement of school teachers in developing the questionnaire. The survey questions were the instrument for gathering quantitative data. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools, where my target participants were, were observed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as explained in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teacher learning assessment capability and student classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City, the significant relationship between teacher learning assessment capability and student classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City, and the influence of teacher learning assessment capability on student classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City.

3.1. Teacher's Learning Assessment Capability In Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City—

3.1.1. *Attitudes towards Self and Peer Assessment*—Regarding attitudes towards self and peer assessment, it shows an extensive category mean rating of 4.19, which means that this domain of teachers' learning assessment capability is often observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.88 to 4.31. The item, showing peer assessment improves students, reflects a mean rating of 3.88, described as extensive and interpreted as an often-observed item. Meanwhile, the item showing peer assessment improves students, shows a rating of 4.31, is defined as very extensive, and is interpreted as always observed. This suggests that

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' learning assessment capability and students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers' learning assessment capability) and dependent (students' classroom satisfaction) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by r . Multiple linear regression was applied to evaluate which domains of the teachers' learning assessment capability significantly predict the students' classroom satisfaction.

the respondents oftentimes observed the evaluation process, on how they will judge their own achievements concerning their own personal criteria, when applying self and peer assessment to learners. The result showed that students become empowered by the learning assessment utilized by the teachers because they were provided with the opportunity to reflect objectively on their own accomplishments and learning. This finding supports the idea of Alufohai and Akinlosotu (2016). Also, this finding supports the view of Olatomide and Oluwatosin (2014) that self-assessment is an effective means of developing independent learning and helpful in changing perceptions of learning in terms of skills and performance.

Table 1. Extent of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in Terms of Attitudes Towards Self and Peer Assessment

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Showing that portfolio assessment makes a great contribution to education.	4.22	Very Extensive
Showing peer assessment improves students.	4.31	Very Extensive
Showing that using peer assessment forms is very important.	4.27	Very Extensive
Showing that self-assessment forms must be used.	4.22	Very Extensive
Showing peer assessment does have importance on students’ development.	3.88	Extensive
Showing that self-assessment improves students’ critical thinking.	4.24	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.19	Extensive

3.1.2. *Attitudes towards using Performance Assessment in Classroom*—This dimension, attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom, shows that its mean score is 4.16, described as extensive, which means that this particular dimension of teachers’ learning assessment capability is oftentimes observed by the respondents in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. The table further reveals that

the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.76 to 4.39. It is noteworthy that item, thinking that it is important to apply performance task, has a mean rating of 3.76, described as extensive, interpreted as this descriptor on this particular indicator is oftentimes observed while item, showing that it is important to use a rubric for assessment of performance tasks has a mean rating of 4.39, described as very extensive and interpreted as always observed.

Table 2. Extent of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in Terms of Attitudes Towards Self and Peer Assessment

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Having a great pleasure when preparing performance tasks.	4.34	Very Extensive
Showing that preparations of rubrics are necessary for performance assessment.	4.37	Very Extensive
Thinking that it is very easy to prepare for performance tasks.	3.81	Extensive
Showing that it is important to use rubrics for the assessment of performance tasks.	4.39	Very Extensive
Developing their selves through performance assessment.	4.15	Extensive
Thinking that performance assessment does have worth.	4.36	Very Extensive
Showing that students will learn better through performance assessment.	4.17	Extensive
Showing that students’ level increases through performance assessment.	4.24	Very Extensive
Having great pleasure from the application of performance assessment in the classroom.	4.07	Extensive
Applying performance assessment in the classroom.	4.15	Extensive
Getting interested in doing performance assessments in classrooms continually.	4.18	Extensive
Thinking that it is a privilege to practice performance assessment in the classroom.	4.09	Extensive
Thinking that it is important to apply performance tasks.	3.76	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.16	Extensive

The extensive rating on attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom implies that the respondents oftentimes observed the teachers’ attitude in preparing and applying the performance assessment that requires students to demonstrate acquisition of knowledge and skills in one or more content areas. This finding supports the argument of Jorge (2013) that the use of performance assessment in the classroom provides pedagogical templates that help teachers to develop effective instructional techniques; and. provides comprehensive information about student progress, including students’ strengths and weaknesses. Also, this supports the proposition of Ong (2013) that performance-based assessment gives attention to the process, product, and on doing something rather than just knowing.

3.1.3. *Attitude towards Authentic Assessment*—The table shows that the dimension, attitude towards authentic assessment, was assessed by the respondents in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City as extensive with a category mean of 2.20, interpreted as seldom observed. The

mean rating of the different items ranges from 1.83 to 2.42. On the one hand, the item showing that performance assessment is worth of time has a mean rating of 1.83, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed. Further, the item showing that students were given freedom with performance tasks reflects a mean of 2.42, described as less extensive, and interpreted as seldom observed. This finding means that the respondents seldom observed the descriptors in this particular domain. The results indicate that the teachers draw from their disposition to form their attitude, which may likely affect their performance outcomes, including their preparation and implementation of their performance assessment tool. This result supports the finding of Yara (2011). Adding more, this finding agrees with the idea of Pean (2014) that if teachers showed a positive approach and expertise in creating a performance assessment tool, then students will develop their higher-level thinking and problem-solving skills.

Table 3. Extent of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in Terms of Attitude Towards Authentic Assessment

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Showing that performance assessment is not expensive.	2.09	Less Extensive
Showing that performance assessment does not take too much time.	2.17	Less Extensive
Showing that performance assessment is worth of time.	1.83	Less Extensive
Showing that students were given freedom with performance tasks.	2.42	Less Extensive
Applying performance assessment in the classroom.	2.34	Less Extensive
Showing that it is very difficult to apply performance assessment.	2.37	Less Extensive
Showing that performance assessment is appropriate for each student.	1.88	Less Extensive
Showing portfolio assessment makes any contributions for students.	2.27	Less Extensive
Showing that portfolio assessment is not a waste of time.	2.22	Less Extensive
Showing that portfolio assessment is not expensive.	2.30	Less Extensive
Showing that self-assessment forms are not necessary.	2.29	Less Extensive
Overall Mean	2.20	Less Extensive

3.1.4. *Table 4 Summarizes The Extent Of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in*

Cluster 2, Davao City—As shown in the table, the overall mean of the teacher’s learning as-

assessment capability is 3.52, which is described as extensive. It means that the teacher’s attitude towards performance assessment is oftentimes observed. The results on the table also showed that teachers’ learning assessment in terms of attitudes towards self and peer assessment acquired the highest mean score of 4.19,

described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the respondents. Meanwhile, teachers’ learning assessment in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment acquired the lowest mean score of 2.20, described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed by the respondents.

Table 4. Summary of the Extent of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Attitudes towards Using Performance Assessment in Classroom	4.16	Extensive
Attitude towards Authentic Assessment	2.20	Less Extensive
Attitudes Towards Self and Peer Assessment	4.19	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.52	Extensive

The extensive rating on teachers’ learning assessment capability supports Sanchez’s (2020) study, which found that teachers’ attitudes towards performance assessment affect students’ ability to apply the skills and knowledge learned from a unit of analysis. The finding emphasizes that the respondents oftentimes perceived that performance assessment is more on task and challenges students to use their higher-order thinking skills to create a product or complete a process. Likewise, the finding supports Yu’s (2014) view that teachers’ attitudes towards performance assessments help engage students in real-world tasks rather than multiple-choice tests and evaluate them according to criteria that are important for actual performance in a field of work.

3.2. *Student’s Classroom Satisfaction In Cluster 2 Schools In Davao City—*

3.2.1. *Contribution—*This dimension has a category mean of 3.98, which is described as extensive and interpreted as students’ classroom satisfaction in terms of contribution, which is oftentimes evident in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.79 to 4.10. The item, Seeking an opportunity to augment learning by collaborating on group projects using various resources, reflects a mean rating of 3.79, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident. Considering the quality of education delivered as efficient and effective, the item has a mean rating of 4.10, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident.

The results imply that the contribution of classroom satisfaction to the quality of education, students’ motivation and satisfaction, learning performance, interaction and/or communication among students, and between students and

teachers is oftentimes evident. These findings support the view of Hettiarachchi and Wickramasinghe (2016) that students consider the quality of education delivered to be more efficient and effective, as they can have it as self-paced

Table 5. Extent of Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Terms of Contribution

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Like to use different methods in the classroom.	3.92	Extensive
Liking the materials of different learning strategies.	4.00	Extensive
Presenting the learning and instruction materials in a creative manner.	4.02	Extensive
Considering the quality of education delivered as efficient and effective.	4.10	Extensive
Enjoying self-paced learning.	4.05	Extensive
Seeking opportunity to augment learning by collaborating on group projects using various resources.	3.79	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.98	Extensive

learning. In addition, this finding supports the view of Himmelsbach (2021) that students like to use different learning environments in their courses as well because it offers an opportunity for them to augment their learning by collaborating on group projects using various resources online or by engaging with online organizations and virtual communities in real-time.

3.2.2. *Communication* —Communication reflects a category mean of 3.96, which is described as extensive, which is interpreted as

students’ classroom satisfaction, which is oftentimes evident in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. It can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.89 to 4.04. Using more questionnaires in the class discussions, the item has a mean rating of 3.89, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident. Whereas, the item Prefer to use the questionnaires among the classroom environment for the subjects has a mean of 4.04 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed.

Table 6. Extent of Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Terms of Communication

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Preferring to use forums for different subjects.	3.99	Extensive
Preferring to use questionnaires in the classroom environment for the subjects.	4.04	Extensive
Using more methods of learning.	3.92	Extensive
Using more questionnaires in the class discussions.	3.89	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.96	Extensive

This implies that the effective sharing of information, which results in a shared understanding, is oftentimes evident among the students. The finding supports Kayode’s (2018) notion that effective communication practices and tools strongly impact distance students’ cognitive engagement. Likewise, this agrees with Hettiarachchi and Wickramasinghe (2016) that virtual learning environments improve student

interaction and, as a result, communication with one another and between students and their instructors, that could contribute to using more forums in online learning. According to Himmelsbach (2021), students who suggested using more forums in a virtual learning environment tend to promote an efficient learning process.

3.2.3. *Satisfaction* —In particular, this dimension has a category mean of 3.82, inter-

interpreted as extensive, which means that the students' classroom satisfaction is always evident among the respondents in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.72 to 3.90. The item, Being contented with the learning environment used in the course, reflects a mean rating of 3.72, described as extensive, interpreted as a descriptor oftentimes evident. Meanwhile, the item, Being contented with the messages and announcements that are announced, acquired the mean rating of 3.90, described as extensive and interpreted as students' classroom satisfaction descriptors are oftentimes evident. The result suggests that the respondents oftentimes observed that the students are satisfied with the instructor, learner,

technology, course, design, and environment. The finding is in consonance with the study of Asoodar et al. (2016) that virtual learning environment students prefer to decrease their ambivalence toward formal education by gaining some sense of a carefully delineated path to success. These students prefer active rather than passive learning environments, and because they participate in a highly interactive world, they expect the same in their classes. Also, the finding is parallel to the findings of Himmelsbach (2021) that students who are contented with the presentation of the course via online learning setup environment increased their engagement, encouraged collaboration, sparked innovation, and enhanced student in learning.

Table 7. Extent of Students' Classroom Satisfaction in Terms of Satisfaction

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Being content with the learning environment used in the course.	3.72	Extensive
Being contented with the learning and teaching materials presented within the course via classroom environment.	3.80	Extensive
Being contented with the messages and announcements that are announced.	3.90	Extensive
Being contented with the presentation of the course.	3.80	Extensive
Being contented with the questionnaires employed.	3.89	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.82	Extensive

3.2.4. *Extent Of Students' Classroom Satisfaction*—Lastly, Table 8 summarizes the extent of students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. The overall mean of the students' classroom satisfaction is 3.92, described as extensive. It means that the students' positive attitude towards web-based communications platforms that allow them, without limitation of time and place, to utilize different learning tools and materials is oftentimes manifested. Adding more results to the table indicates that the overall mean score is acquired due to the mean score of 3.82 or extensive on

satisfaction, 3.96 or extensive on communication, and 3.98 or extensive on contribution. This finding is similar to the study of Elshami et al. (2021), which found that virtual learning environment satisfaction is multidimensional and complex. Thus, satisfaction with virtual learning is significant in promoting successful educational processes. Likewise, this result agrees with the argument of Alawamleh and Al-twait (2020) that students with a positive perception of the virtual learning environment appear to be engaged, motivated, and responsive, contribute to an effective learning climate, and achieve a higher level of interest.

Table 8. Summary of the Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Satisfaction	3.82	Extensive
Communication	3.96	Extensive
Contribution	3.98	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.92	Extensive

3.3. *Relationship Between Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability And Students’ Classroom Satisfaction In Cluster 2 Schools In Davao City*—The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers’ learning assessment capability and students’ classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City are presented in Table 9. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. It shows that teachers’ learning assessment capability has a significant positive relationship with the student’s classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000

that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.496, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the teachers’ learning assessment capability changes, students’ classroom satisfaction also significantly changes. Moreover, the results in the table showed that Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability in terms of attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitudes towards authentic assessment, and attitudes towards self and peer assessment has a significant positive relationship with the student’s classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.552, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.668, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.734, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 9. Relationship Between Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability and Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Attitudes towards Using Performance Assessment in Classroom	0.552*	0.000	Significant	Reject H
Attitude towards Authentic Assessment	0.668*	0.000	Significant	Reject H
Attitudes Towards Self and Peer Assessment	0.734*	0.000	Significant	Reject H
Overall Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability	0.496*	0.000	Significant	Reject H

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$.

The findings agree with the proposition of Ugras et al.(2012) that satisfaction in on-line setting could be established by connecting teacher’s skills and knowledge about various assessment tools and techniques. Thus, a teacher needs to have a good command of the concepts in performance assessment, specific skills, and

positive attitudes to evaluate and develop their teaching methods and reach fewer value judgments. Students’ satisfaction in a virtual environment and teachers’ attitudes towards assessment are essential to success in the distance learning setup.

3.4. *Influence of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability on the Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Cluster 2 in Schools in Davao City*—The significance of teachers’ learning assessment capability on students’ classroom satisfaction as perceived by the teachers was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 10 shows that when attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitudes towards authentic assessment, and attitudes towards self and peer assessment are considered predictors of students’ classroom

satisfaction, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 113.946 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that teachers’ learning assessment capability predicts the students’ classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.430 indicates that teachers’ capability has contributed significantly to the variability of students’ classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City by 43.00 percent from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 57.00 percent was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

Table 10. Influence of Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability on the Students’ Classroom Satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City

Teachers’ Learning Assessment Capability Decisions	B	Beta	S.E	p-value
Attitudes towards Using Performance Assessment in the Classroom Accept H	-0.102**	0.102	0.078	0.112
Attitude towards Authentic Assessment Reject H	0.594**	0.349	0.083	0.000
Attitudes Towards Self and Peer Assessment Accept H	0.110	0.029	0.082	0.520
R²				0.430
F-value				113.946*
p-value				0.000

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$.

In addition, the table shows that only attitude towards authentic assessment is significant when the predictors are considered. This means that the odds for students’ classroom satisfaction status to be taken increases by 0.594 for each unit increase in the teacher’s capability in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment. Thus, this leads to rejecting the null hypothesis that none of the teachers’ learning assessment capability domains significantly influence the students’ classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. One imperative concern

of this undertaking is to find out whether the findings have supported the theories that serve as this study’s framework. As regards the proposition of Ugras et al. (2012), the result of the study is in agreement that satisfaction in learning could be established by connecting teachers’ skills and knowledge about various assessment tools and techniques. Thus, a teacher needs to have a good command of the concepts in performance assessment, specific skills, and positive attitudes to evaluate and develop their teaching methods and reach fewer value judgments.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the findings were supported by the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The study primarily aimed to determine which domain of teachers' learning assessment capability significantly influences students' classroom satisfaction utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using correlation technique. The researcher selected the 200 secondary school teachers in Cluster 2, Division of Davao City, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The summary of the findings based on the results was presented. The extent of teachers' learning assessment capability in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.52, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. Also, teachers' learning assessment capability in terms of attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitude towards authentic assessment, and attitudes towards self and peer assessment obtained the mean scores of 4.16, 2.20, and 4.19, respectively. The extent of students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.92, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident. Also, students' classroom satisfaction, communication, and contribution obtained the mean scores of 3.82, 3.96, and 3.98, respectively. The result showed teachers' learning assessment capability in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City has a significant positive relationship with students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .496, p < 0.05$). The

extent of teachers' learning assessment capability regarding attitude towards authentic assessment significantly influenced the students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City, as evidenced by the F-value of 113.946 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.430 indicated that teachers' learning assessment capability in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment have contributed significantly to the variability of students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City by 43.00

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated. The teachers' learning assessment capability in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City was rated as extensive. Moreover, teachers' learning assessment capability in terms of attitudes towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitude towards authentic assessment, and attitudes towards self and peer assessment obtained an extensive descriptive rating. In contrast, teachers' capability in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment got a less extensive rating. The student's classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City was rated as extensive. In addition, students' classroom satisfaction, communication, and contribution are descriptively rated as extensive. The result showed that teachers' learning assessment capability has a significant positive relationship with students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City. As the extent of the teachers' learning assessment capability changes, students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City also significantly changes. The extent of teachers' learning assessment capability in terms of attitude towards authentic assessment significantly influ-

enced students' classroom satisfaction in Cluster 2 Schools in Davao City.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the conclusion generated in this study, the researcher recommends the following: This study found that teachers' learning assessment capability is extensive. The researcher recommends that the Department of Education continue to provide educators with an orientation that might give them adequate background and knowledge and usable information on how to apply responsive performance assessment tools and strategies. This type of orientation would best allow teachers to integrate performance-based assessment in meaningful ways at the classroom level.

School administrators should provide teachers with intensive ICT-based training to equip them with knowledge of ICT and its utilization in mathematics teaching. It was further suggested that school administrators and stakeholders may look for interventions to upgrade the

school's ICT-based resources for their optimum use in teaching and learning. Most importantly, a larger school-wide ICT development plan may be implemented to ensure coherence of ICT implementation in the teaching-learning activities. Moreover, since the student's classroom satisfaction was extensive and can still be sustained or maintained if teachers embrace digital communication through emails, student chat rooms, social media channels, online forums, and more, it was the key to increasing the effectiveness of online learning. Students can interact with classmates and raise doubts about the course and assignments. Since the result revealed an R^2 of 0.43, which implies that 57.00 percent of the variation can be attributed to other variables or factors not covered in the study, an exploratory study on the factors that influenced the students' classroom satisfaction should be conducted.

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